

Tips and tricks for creating and giving a scientific presentation

Version: V1

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Topic

The publication 'Tips and Tricks for Creating and Giving a Scientific Presentation' provides practical advice on design slides and giving a confident presentation in front of a specialist audience.

The article is part of a more comprehensive article on 'Good scientific presentation', which consists of three parts: 1-Criteria of a good scientific presentation, 2-checklist (this article), 3-tips and tricks.

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Aim

The aim of a scientific presentation is to enter into a scientific discourse and professional exchange with the audience.

Listeners

Find out about your target group. It makes a difference whether you are speaking in front of scientists, practitioners, students, politicians, citizens or a mixed audience. Depending on the target audience, different knowledge and interests may be assumed and you should take this into account in your presentation. Try to anticipate potential questions and comments about your presentation from the audience. Before giving your presentation, you should take an objective look at it and find out where

the audience might need further information or clarification. You can prepare yourself for possible questions and discussion points, for example, by incorporating explanatory or in-depth results as an add-on into your presentation or by having further results or additional information 'up your sleeve', e.g. in the form of presentation slides.

§ Formal requirements

Check the formal requirements for the presentation.

These include: time duration of the presentation, format of the slides or poster, technical possibilities or implementation, submission deadlines and procedures in advance, if applicable, and other requirements.

Presentation of results

The presentation of scientific studies is well done appropriate if you present the results descriptively, stating the actual changes or effects. You should favour measures that are easy to understand, direct and suitable for everyday use over abstract, theoretical measures that are difficult to calculate and understand. Statistical tests with the calculation of p-values make statements about the randomness of a difference. P-values can be given in the case of an exploratory evaluation method (the aim is to generate hypotheses) or in the case of a confirmatory evaluation method (the aim is to confirm or refute hypotheses) (Röhrig et al 2009, du Prel et al 2009).

Suitable graphical representations in the form of meaningful histograms, bar charts, box-whisker plots, error diagrams, scatter plots and progression plots help listeners to quickly absorb and store the information presented (Spriestersbach 2009, Weissgerber et al 2015, Weissgerber et al 2017, Weissgerber et al 2019). When choosing the appropriate figure, consider the scale level (simplified: categorical, ordinal or interval-scaled) and whether the variables are independent or dependent. In general, the presentation of the results should be as objective, simple and clear as possible, also to distinguish it from art (Rougier et al 2014).

Further information and tips on how to present statistical content well can be found in extensive textbooks (Sachs 2003, Weiß 2019, Bortz 2005) as well as in suitable publications (Spriesterbach et al 2009, Röhrig et al 2009, Faller 2004, Weissgerber et al 2015, Weissgerber et al 2017, Weissgerber et al 2019).

Create slides with a suitable presentation program

Create a clear presentation, for example with the presentation software 'Power Point'.

A good presentation is structured, easy to read (even in the last row!), as 'calm' as possible (sparing change of font, font size and colour, no bright or pale colour, uniform indentation) and contains well-worked and clearly designed slides. On the slides, you should include as little text as possible, i.e. only keywords/short sentences, only main points and no marginal information.

At the end of a presentation, there should be a slide with one (or more) "Take Home Message(s)". The 'Take Home Message(s)' enables the audience to remember the most important aspects and, if necessary, to take them into account in their medical practice.

A complete presentation gives you confidence and makes it easier for your presentation to succeed!

- Familiarize yourself with the presentation program!
- If you have mastered the technology of the software, can use it confidently and know important commands from the menu as well as suitable key combinations, this expands presentation options.

Useful tips for presenting with PowerPoint

- Start of presentation: <F5>
 - Start of presentation, from current slide: <Shift+F5>
 - End of the presentation: <ESC>
 - Calling up the menu with further commands, during the presentation: right mouse button
 - Next slide / next: <Spacebar>, <ENTER key ↵>, < Page button ↓>, < Page button →>, left mouse button
 - Last slide / backwards: < Page button ↑>, < Page button ←>
 - Start of the presentation (first slide): <Pos1>
 - End of the presentation (last slide): <End>
 - Switching to a specific page: Page Number + <ENTER Key ↵>
 - Hide with black background:
 - Hide with white background: <f>
 - Return to the presentation: any key
- Figures and graphics are tied to the data and you should present them objectively, clearly and as simply as possible: Content is above beauty!

- Suitable images, photos and graphics loosen up your presentation and make it clearer. The short article 'Use images for free and royalty-free' provides tips for media that can be used free of charge:

Röhrig, B. (2025). Use images for free and royalty-free. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851966>.

You must ensure correct citation and copyright protection when using third-party images and graphics. For more information, please visit: <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses>.

Giving a presentation

- Give yourself or your colleagues a rehearsal of your presentation before the actual presentation. This will give you confidence and give you a feeling for any problems and critical passages. You can use the checklist for this:
Röhrig, B., Exner, A.-K., Klemmt, M. (2025). Evaluation of a scientific presentation using a checklist. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064504>.
- Before giving the presentation, familiarize yourself with the room (size, lighting conditions, presentation desk, etc.) and the technology in the room, for example during a break. If you have any questions, please feel free to speak to the supervisors in the lecture room. This will calm you down and help you to concentrate on the content during the presentation.
- Stick to the allowed time! Stop the time it takes when rehearsing the lecture. This will help you develop a feeling for the length of your presentation.

We wish you every success and good luck with your presentation!

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